

Selective deep water coral bleaching occurs through depth isolation

Authors

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Highlights

- Mesophotic communities are not immune from coral bleaching, are in danger, and are degrading in the Red Sea.
- Heat accumulation at mesophotic depths is almost twofold higher than on adjacent shallow reefs.
- Bleaching events affect the deep-specialist coral populations, with ~50% coral community mortality at 60 m depth between the years 2010 and 2018.
- The deeper benthic community lost framework builders and high relief areas, may result in lower complexity, fewer niches, and loss of biodiversity.
- Experimental evidence suggests that, in contrast to depth-generalist corals, deep-specialist corals are less tolerant of heat stress and bleach more readily.

25 **Abstract**

26 Climate change is degrading coral reefs around the world. Mass coral bleaching events have become
27 more frequent in recent decades, leading to dramatic declines in coral cover. Mesophotic coral
28 ecosystems (30-150 m depth) comprise an estimated 50–80% of global coral reef area. The potential
29 for these to act as refuges from climate change is unresolved. Here, we report three mesophotic-
30 specific coral bleaching events in the northern Red Sea over the course of eight years. Over the last
31 decade, faster temperature increases at mesophotic depths resulted in ~50% decline in coral
32 populations, while the adjacent shallow coral reefs remained intact. Further, community structure
33 shifted from hard coral dominated to turf algae dominated throughout these recurrent bleaching
34 events. Our results do not falsify the notion of the northern Red Sea as a thermal refuge for shallow
35 coral reefs, but question the capacity of mesophotic ecosystems to act as a universal tropical refuge.

36

37 **Keywords**

38 climate change, thermal tolerance, global warming, deep coral reefs, mesophotic coral ecosystems
39 (MCEs), refugia, refuge, Red Sea, deep-specialist, depth-generalist

40 **Introduction**

41 Coral bleaching is one of the greatest contributors to global coral reef decline (Hughes,
42 Anderson et al. 2018). Reefs worldwide are experiencing severe degradation, most recently due to
43 anthropogenic-induced thermal stress. However, shallow coral reefs (i.e., 0–30 m depth) in the high-
44 latitude northern sections of the Red Sea are posited to be a refuge from ocean warming (Osman,
45 Smith et al. 2018). Hermatypic (reef-building) corals in the northern Red Sea are recorded along a
46 wide depth gradient down to 145 m (Fricke and Schuhmacher 1983). Coral reefs flourish at shallow
47 and mesophotic depths (i.e., 30-150 m depth) due to the clarity of the oligotrophic water in the region
48 (Eyal, Tamir et al. 2019). Globally, deeper light-dependent coral ecosystems are suggested to be less
49 susceptible to coral bleaching due to the lower temperatures, reduced irradiance, and atmospheric

50 effects with increasing depth (Glynn 1996, Lesser, Slattery et al. 2009). The lack of knowledge about
51 mesophotic ecosystems signifies a large gap in our understanding of coral reefs globally, including
52 the northern Red Sea coral reefs (Loya, Eyal et al. 2016).

53 The Red Sea basin is around 2000 km long and 230 km wide (**Fig. 1A**). It diverges into the
54 Gulf of Suez and the Gulf of Eilat/Aqaba in the north and is connected to the Gulf of Aden via the
55 Bab el Mandeb straits in the south. The Bab el Mandeb straits are relatively shallow (~137 m deep)
56 and are divided by Perim Island into a smaller and larger channel. Most of the water circulation is
57 facilitated by the larger channel and the flow pattern is controlled by a sill situated at the northernmost
58 part of the straits. The basic circulation pattern involves an inflow of water adjacent to the surface
59 from the Gulf of Aden through the Bab el Mandeb straits and outflow through the bottom of the sill
60 (Siedler 1969, Siddall, Smeed et al. 2004). New Gulf of Aden Surface Water (GASW; water from the
61 surface of the Indian Ocean) enters the southern Red Sea via the straits, flows northward, and
62 undergoes large rates of evaporation to form Red Sea Water (RSW) in the northernmost section. This
63 results in hot and saline Red Sea Deep Water (RSDW; ~21.5°C and 41‰, respectively) along the
64 entire basin, as it is isolated from the oceanic global water circulation. This in turn creates uniquely
65 appropriate environmental conditions for the development of productive coral reefs at a latitude of
66 ~30° north, despite vertical deep-mixing events in the area (Genin, Lazar et al. 1995). RSW flows
67 south as a salty, high-density layer of cold water, yet below this layer, a relatively stationary layer of
68 denser RSDW remains. Depending on the season, the mode of Red Sea water exchange with the
69 Indian Ocean differs. During the winter, GASW enters above the layer of RSW forming a dominant
70 2-layer system and the RSDW exits the Red Sea at a slower rate than normal. During the summer, at
71 the same time of the year in which most corals reproduce in the Red Sea (Shlesinger and Loya 1985),
72 the level of Gulf of Aden Intermediate Water (GAIW) increases and penetrates the southern part of
73 the Red Sea as an intermediate layer. This layer persists for a few months before merging with the

74 upper layer of RSW (Siddall, Smeed et al. 2004). The cold (16–19°C) GAIW enters the Red Sea at
75 depths of 50–100 m in the straits of Perim (Maillard and Soliman 1986, Sofianos, Johns et al. 2002).

76 During the Last Glacial Maximum (LGM) event that ended ~10 thousand years ago, global
77 sea level fell by at least 120 m. The water depth in Bab el Mandeb sill dropped to less than 15 m,
78 thereby restricting the volume of GASW entering the Red Sea from the Indian Ocean (Siddall,
79 Rohling et al. 2003). Subsequent evaporation increased salinity to levels likely inhospitable to corals
80 (Sirocko 2003, Biton, Gildor et al. 2008). During this period of hyper salinity, there was an
81 accumulation of organic-rich sediments and a humid climate persisted (Arz, Lamy et al. 2003). Over
82 the past 6–8 thousand years, after sea-level rose to present-day levels, corals started to recolonise the
83 basin. Since then the climate has been predominantly dry, with super oligotrophic water. These
84 conditions allowed the proliferation and growth of coral reefs across the Red Sea coastal waters
85 (Thunell, Locke et al. 1988, Arz, Lamy et al. 2003). A horizontal thermal barrier at the southern
86 section of the Red Sea (**Fig. 1A**) is hypothesized to have created positive selection pressure for taxa
87 resistant to high temperatures when colonizing the northern reefs after the sealevel rose (Fine, Gildor
88 et al. 2013). This horizontal thermal barrier in the shallow waters (< 50 m depth) of the southern Red
89 Sea likely still exists because of the unique climatological conditions and oceanography of the region.
90 The barrier may continue to shape a unique, thermally-tolerant coral community in shallow waters
91 (Fine, Gildor et al. 2013, Osman, Smith et al. 2018). Accordingly, a mass coral bleaching event has
92 never been reported from reefs of the northern Red Sea, despite severe recurring bleaching on many
93 reefs worldwide, including the warmer shallow water of the southern Red Sea (Furby, Bouwmeester
94 et al. 2013, Osman, Smith et al. 2018).

95 Below this horizontal thermal barrier at the southern Red Sea, Mesophotic Coral Ecosystems
96 (MCEs) exist (**Fig. 1B**). MCEs located between depths of 30–150 m, are generally considered less
97 likely to suffer coral bleaching than their shallow water counterparts. The deep-reef-refugia
98 hypothesis (DRRH) has proposed MCEs may serve as possible refugia for shallow water taxa, as

99 deeper waters are thought to be protected from stressors and disturbance (Bongaerts, Ridgway et al.
100 2010). Studies investigating the DRRH suggest it only applies in specific cases (Bongaerts, Riginos
101 et al. 2017, Frade, Bongaerts et al. 2018), and MCEs are in fact threatened by various anthropogenic,
102 climatic, and natural disturbances similarly to shallow reefs (Smith, Gyory et al. 2016, Rocha,
103 Pinheiro et al. 2018, Pinheiro, Eyal et al. 2019, de Oliveira Soares, de Araújo et al. 2020). The
104 frequency and intensity of such disturbances, however, decrease with depth in the northern Red Sea
105 (Eyal, Tamir et al. 2019).

106 The geological history, and the resultant environmental conditions of the Red Sea, provide
107 the conditions for possible vertical isolation along the depth gradient and a hypothetical mechanism
108 for the stratified patterns we observe in coral bleaching (**Fig. 1B**). We report on long-term field
109 observations and in situ monitoring that captures deep water mass coral bleaching and the impact it
110 has on the mesophotic coral ecosystem in the northern Red Sea. We used a multidisciplinary approach
111 of: repetitive benthic surveys, long-term environmental monitoring, in situ analyses of coral
112 physiological performance, and manipulative heat stress experiments to understand how selective
113 coral bleaching occurred in the deep environment.

114

115 **Methods**

116 **Long-term environmental conditions**

117 For almost two decades the Israeli National Monitoring Program (NMP) of the Gulf of Eilat
118 has monitored the meteorological conditions, oceanographical regimes, and ecological status of coral
119 reefs in the northern Red Sea (Shaked and Genin 2020). Shallow water (~2 m depth) in situ
120 temperature measurements were recorded at 10 minute intervals. Monthly conductivity, temperature,
121 and depth (CTD) profiler casts were performed along the entire depth gradient down to ~700 m,
122 approximately 4 km from the reef (**Fig. S1**). For this research, we deployed additional in situ
123 temperature loggers at 3 m, 5–10 m and 45–50 m for the entire period of July 21st 2011 to September

124 1st 2017 and at 60 m for the summer period of 2018, from July 11th to September 5th, on the reef in
125 front of the Interuniversity Institute for Marine Sciences (IUI) (**Fig. S1**). Temperature was further
126 analyzed for thermal dynamics from both NMP data and our loggers.

127 In addition to in situ measurements, we also retrieved daily remote-sensing sea-surface
128 temperature (SST) data for the last 35 years at the Gulf of Eilat/Aqaba. We used the 5 km Regional
129 Bleaching Heat Stress Time Series data product (Version 3.1) (NOAA Coral Reef Watch 2021) to
130 calculate regional SST thermal dynamics and compared them to the local in situ measurements to
131 quantify measurement error and cross-correlation coefficients.

132 To determine the long-term Maximum Monthly Mean (MMM) for our open ocean CTD
133 measurements, we took the hottest temperature in August during 2003-2019 and averaged those
134 temperatures by depth bin to get the MMM per depth bin. We used the MMM determined over this
135 period for the in situ data as well, for example, the MMM determined for the depth bin 49-62m from
136 the CTD was applied to the 45-50m in situ logged data.

137

138 **Bleaching observations and quantification**

139 Mesophotic benthic observations at 50–65 m depth were conducted annually from June 2010
140 to December 2020. When coral mass bleaching became apparent at the end of 2010, 2015 and 2018,
141 we conducted photographic surveys of 30–32 quadrat plots of 0.35 m² in front of the Interuniversity
142 Institute for Marine Sciences in Eilat (IUI). All surveys were done by SCUBA using closed circuit
143 rebreathers (CCRs) or open-circuit apparatuses. Survey photos were annotated in CoralNet (Beijbom,
144 Edmunds et al. 2012), with 100 sampling points per photo in two stages, first to quantify benthic
145 community structure using percent cover of major benthic groups, and second to quantify the
146 percentage cover of bleached, partially bleached, and non-bleached coral colonies. Anecdotal
147 bleaching observations were recorded for 2019 (N. Kramer, personal observation) and 2020 (Y.
148 Lindemann, personal observation), but these were not quantitative surveys.

149

150 **Temporal changes in benthic community composition and coral morphotype cover**

151 Shifts in benthic communities were visualized using non-parametric multidimensional scaling
152 (nMDS) using a Bray-Curtis dissimilarity matrix of square-root transformed cover data. Seven
153 ecologically important benthic groups were included in the analysis: hard corals, soft corals, sponges,
154 macroalgae, turf algae, crustose coralline algae (CCA), and black corals. We performed a multiple
155 permutational analysis of variance (PERMANOVA) to determine significant differences in benthic
156 composition among years. Pairwise PERMANOVA was used to identify significant differences
157 among years.

158 Stacked bar charts were used to illustrate relative changes in the percent cover for each of the
159 mass bleaching years (2010, 2015 and 2018) for the morphological groups (branching, encrusting,
160 massive, and plate-like) according to their health status (bleached, partially bleached, and non-
161 bleached). Due to violations of parametric test assumptions (e.g., normality and homogeneity of
162 variances), we used a permutational ANOVA approach to assess differences in percent cover among
163 years, morphotypes, and health status. When significant differences were found, permutational t-tests
164 (999 permutations) were applied. All the analyses were performed in the R programming environment
165 (Team 2013), using the *vegan* (Oksanen, Blanchet et al. 2013), *RVAideMemoire* (Hervé and Hervé
166 2020), and *lme4* (Bates, Sarkar et al. 2007) packages.

167

168 **Physiological capacity of depth-generalists and deep-specialists corals to thermal stress**

169 To assess the photosynthetic performance of mesophotic corals during the mass bleaching
170 event of 2018, we used an underwater pulse amplitude modulated fluorometer (Diving-PAM; Walz
171 GmbH, Germany) to conduct in situ rapid light-curve measurements at 60 m. During early morning,
172 with ambient light of $30 \mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{ sec}^{-1}$, the Diving-PAM was used to measure and calculate
173 the effective quantum yield of photosystem- II (Y[II]), non-photochemical quenching (NPQ), and the

174 approximate relative electron transport rate (rETR). Four bleached colonies of *Leptoseris glabra*
175 (deep-specialist species) and four non-bleached colonies of *Porites lutea* (depth-generalist) corals
176 were assessed. Non-bleached colonies of *Leptoseris glabra* could not be found. Chlorophyll *a*
177 fluorescence was measured following a light saturation pulse ($>4000 \mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{sec}^{-1}$, white
178 light, 500 ms) after 2.5 min incubation at increasing actinic light intensities (30, 250, 340, 480, 640,
179 930, 1310, 1890 and $2950 \mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{sec}^{-1}$). Although corals at 60 m will never experience
180 such high intensities, we found it important to measure the depth-generalist corals under these levels.
181 We were not sure how sensitive depth-generalists are to light intensity and were concerned they may
182 harbor shallow water symbionts. To get fair and comparable curves between taxa we used the same
183 induction light levels on all corals, regardless of the risk of photoinhibition with high intensities. The
184 main purpose of the light-curves was to compare between the two groups (bleached and non-bleached
185 corals) at a constant mesophotic depth. The Diving-PAM setup parameters (gain and measuring
186 intensity) were adjusted according to the F_0 of each colony, followed by an auto zero and stabilising
187 of the F_0 before light curve started. In pale and bleached colonies, we occasionally used the highest
188 sensitivity of the device (levels 12) to get a proper signal of F_0 (always above 130 and preferably
189 between 300-700).

190 In 2016, when deep water bleaching did not occur, we conducted aquaria-based thermal
191 experiments on deep-specialist and depth-generalists corals. Six colonies of *L. glabra* (deep-
192 specialist) were sampled (permit no. 2016/41525) at 50 m depth, and seven colonies each of *P. lutea*
193 and *Montipora danae* (depth-generalists; permit no. 2016/41528) were collected at 10 m depth at the
194 reef in front of the IUI. All colonies were broken into 4×4 cm fragments, resulting in $n=44$, 32, and
195 29 fragments of *L. glabra*, *P. lutea*, and *M. danae*, respectively. Each fragment was glued to a 5×5
196 cm unglazed terracotta tile using underwater non-toxic epoxy glue. Corals were kept in the running
197 sea water system at the IUI. *L. glabra* fragments were kept under a light barrier filter ("Lagoon blue",
198 LeeFilters, UK) to mimic the mesophotic light environment at 50 m depth. Corals were randomly

199 placed under ambient light in one of two treatments for 14 days: ambient sea temperature (AT; 25°C
200 equivalent to the MMM at 50 m), and high temperature (HT; +4°C above ambient sea temperature,
201 equivalent to the MMM+4°C at 50 m). Water in the HT treatment was heated by 1°C per day, reaching
202 29°C, using three submersible aquarium heaters (250W, Aqua One, China). Temperature and light
203 intensity were recorded during the experiment using HOBO pendant temperature and light data
204 loggers (Onset, USA) at 5 minute intervals. Corals were imaged from a top view at days 1 (T₀), 5
205 (T₁), 10 (T₂), and 13 (T₃) next to the "Coral Health Chart" (CoralWatch, Australia) for colour
206 indication (Siebeck, Marshall et al. 2006). Maximal photosynthetic yield (F_v/F_m) was measured (n=3
207 measurements for each fragment at each sampling point) using the Diving-PAM on the same days
208 (i.e., T₀-T₃) an hour after sunset to assure all photosystem-II reaction centres were vacant. In 2016,
209 we conducted aquaria experiments only and not in situ PAM surveys. Instead, we used the Diving-
210 PAM to verify the maximal quantum yield (F_v/F_m) of several species under temperature stress in
211 aquaria, not in the field. In 2018 we were not able to get a permit for collecting colonies, so we used
212 light-curves as a non-extractive method of assessment of the photobiology of these corals.

213

214 **Results**

215 Despite the hypothesized Red Sea refuge (Fine, Gildor et al. 2013) and the DRRH (Bongaerts,
216 Ridgway et al. 2010), we report observed repetitive, severe, mass coral bleaching events on the MCEs
217 of the northern Red Sea. These events took place in three non-consecutive years in the last decade:
218 2010, 2015 and 2018 (**Fig. 2A**) and were also observed, but not quantified, in 2019 and 2020
219 (Extended Data **Fig. S2**). These mesophotic-specific coral bleaching events corresponded with sharp
220 temperature increases at mesophotic depths (**Table 1; Fig. 2**) and resulted in a large decline in coral
221 populations over the last decade (**Fig. 3A,B**). The events were species-specific and mostly affected
222 the specialized deep hermatypic corals displaying plate-like (tabular/foliose/laminar) growth forms,

223 but also impacted other coral morphotypes (**Fig. 3B; Fig. S2**). Further, community structure shifted
224 to lower hard-coral and higher turf-algae cover throughout these recurrent bleaching events (**Fig. 3A**).

225 The exposure of the mesophotic corals to increased thermal stress has resulted in significant
226 community-level changes (PERMANOVA, $F= 63.056$, $p < 0.001$). Specifically, a 46% decline in
227 hard coral cover between 2010 and 2018 was observed in response to the mass bleaching events (**Fig.**
228 **3A**). Consequently, these communities are no longer dominated by hard corals and have shifted
229 toward turf algae throughout the decade. While there can be other causes of coral mortality within
230 mesophotic ecosystems (Rocha, Pinheiro et al. 2018), none have been observed to induce such a
231 change in community structure. Substantial differences in coral cover were found between years and
232 among hard coral morphological groups (permutational ANOVA, $F_{\text{YEAR}}= 9.429$, $F_{\text{MORPH}}= 30.528$, p
233 < 0.001). Throughout the last decade, plate-like corals were the most affected by bleaching, as
234 indicated by a decline in coral cover (**Fig. 3B**). In 2010, nearly three-quarters (73.8%) of all coral
235 colonies were either fully or partially bleached. Of the bleached colonies, plate-like corals were
236 bleached at least three-fold more than any other morphological group (**Fig 3B**). Despite the reduced
237 abundance of these corals over time, plate-like corals continued to show a high bleaching proportion,
238 compared to other morphological groups, in both 2015 and 2018 (**Fig 3B**). These findings suggest
239 that the ability of plate-like corals and possibly other deep-specialist corals to persist at mesophotic
240 depths might be jeopardised by ongoing bleaching events.

241 Water temperatures have increased sharply over the last two decades in the northern Red Sea,
242 in both bleaching-affected reefs as well as the adjacent non-affected shallow reefs (**Table 1; Fig. 2**).
243 Monthly measurements taken by the Israel National Monitoring Program at the Gulf of Eilat (NMP)
244 (Shaked and Genin 2020) show that deeper water layers (below 38 m depth) are warming at a faster
245 rate than shallower water layers (0–21 m). The highest increase per decade was observed within 49–
246 62 m (+0.48°C) compared to an increase of +0.31°C between 7–21 m (**Fig. 2A**) and to global average
247 increases of +0.18–0.19°C per decade (Dunn, Stanitski et al. 2020). As a result, degree heating weeks

248 (DHW) accumulated mostly in the deep-water environment, with temperatures passing the threshold
249 for bleaching (Glynn and D'croz 1990) in the summer for six of the seven years that we measured
250 (**Table 1; Fig. 2B**). In the shallow depths, temperature records were generally below the bleaching
251 threshold, or exceeded it for short periods (**Table 1- 'Degree heating days'; Fig. 2B**). From our seven
252 years of in situ high-resolution temperature measurements, DHW crossed the assumed coral mortality
253 threshold (i.e., $DHW > 8^{\circ}\text{C week}^{-1}$) (Kayanne 2017) only in 2015 at the 45–50 m depth. Currently,
254 thermal stress on coral reefs is identified globally by remote sensing (e.g. (NOAA Coral Reef Watch
255 2021), which does not detect temperatures below 10 m depth (Heron, Heron et al. 2013). We found
256 discrepancies between our in situ shallow and deep temperature measurements and DHW calculated
257 from remote sensing data (NOAA Coral Reef Watch 2021), which highlights the inability to identify
258 thermal stress in deeper environments without in situ temperature measurements (**Table 1; 2; Fig. 2;**
259 **Fig. S3; S4; S5; S6**).

260 In addition to trends in temperature, we found evidence that some deep-specialist corals are
261 more vulnerable to changes in temperature and performed less efficiently physiologically during
262 bleaching in both field and laboratory conditions (**Figs. S7; S8**). In situ photosynthetic performance
263 measurements taken at 60 m depth during the 2018 bleaching event showed a $37.1 \pm 9.8\%$ (mean \pm SD)
264 lower effective quantum yield of photosystem II ($Y[\text{II}]$), $46 \pm 9.1\%$ higher non-photochemical
265 quenching (NPQ), and $42 \pm 9.2\%$ lower relative electron transport rates (rETR) for selected bleached
266 deep-specialist corals compared to non-bleached depth-generalist corals (**Fig. S7**). Apparently, for
267 both taxa assessed photoinhibition started around the same light intensity level ($\sim 1000 \mu\text{moles}$
268 $\text{photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) regardless of the lower rETR_{max} of the deep-specialist corals. Furthermore, when
269 experimentally testing the response of the deep-specialist coral *Leptoseris glabra* from 50 m to
270 thermal stress compared to two depth-generalist coral species (*Porites lutea* and *Montipora danae*)
271 from the shallow reef, we observed, in *L. glabra*, a significant decrease of 57% in maximal quantum

272 yield of photosystem II (F_v/F_m). This was accompanied by visually apparent bleaching after only nine
273 days exposure to +4°C above the averaged maximum monthly mean (MMM) at this depth (**Fig. S8**).

274

275 **Discussion**

276 Accurate data on the temporal patterns of coral bleaching are essential, both for understanding
277 how coral ecosystems are being altered and predicting their future in an era of continuing climate
278 change. The history of past coral bleaching events in most regions of the world is increasingly
279 documented but is poorly studied in the northern Red Sea (Hughes, Anderson et al. 2018, Monroe,
280 Ziegler et al. 2018). This is especially true on MCEs (Eyal, Tamir et al. 2019). We propose that
281 bleaching in the mesophotic ecosystem of the northern Red Sea occurs because deep-specialist coral
282 species in the region are less resistant to high temperatures than shallow taxa. As the larvae of deep-
283 specialist corals originate at depths of approximately 50–100 m, they may pass under the thermal
284 barrier in the southern Red Sea, along the subsurface intrusion of the Gulf of Aden Intermediate Water
285 (GAIW) (Maillard and Soliman 1986, Sofianos, Johns et al. 2002, Dreano, Raitos et al. 2016). These
286 corals in the northern Red Sea, therefore, resemble the southern coral populations that experience the
287 cooler GAIW temperatures (16–19°C in summer months cf. 30°C in the shallows of the northern Red
288 Sea) (Maillard and Soliman 1986, Sofianos, Johns et al. 2002, Wafar, Ashraf et al. 2016), possibly
289 still maintaining horizontal connectivity with the Indian Ocean populations. This means the larvae
290 avoid, or skip, the selective pressure for high thermal tolerance that renders shallow and depth-
291 generalist corals resistant to bleaching (**Fig. 1A**). While it is possible that deep-specialist coral larvae
292 disperse at shallow depths and are tolerant to high water temperatures, when they sink and settle in
293 the deep, cooler environment, the adult colonies do not appear to be selectively resistant to high
294 temperature stress and have limited plasticity in their thermal tolerance (Klepac and Barshis 2020,
295 Keshavmurthy, Beals et al. 2021).

296 Mass coral bleaching of shallow coral reefs in the Red Sea is rare, but has been documented
297 in the central and southern parts (<24°N) in 2010 and 2015 (Furby, Bouwmeester et al. 2013, Monroe,
298 Ziegler et al. 2018, Hammerman, Roff et al. 2022). However, in the northern part of the Red Sea,
299 shallow reefs did not experience mass coral bleaching during any of the global coral bleaching events.
300 The corals in this specific region are considered highly tolerant (Fine, Gildor et al. 2013, Osman,
301 Smith et al. 2018). The few MCE coral bleaching events reported from the region (Nir, Gruber et al.
302 2014, Eyal, Tamir et al. 2019, Eyal, Eyal-Shaham et al. 2021) are mostly episodic and limited to one
303 or a few species. In other regions, MCEs are less affected by bleaching, mainly because of lower
304 variability in temperature and light intensity. The unique case of thermally tolerant shallow
305 communities that may not be genetically connected to the deeper communities, along with relatively
306 elevated temperatures deeper in the water column, created the unfortunate situation that deeper
307 communities suffered from mass coral bleaching at least three times over the last decade. It is possible
308 that the mass bleaching in MCEs of the northern Red Sea are due to their longer exposure to thermal
309 stress (Table 1) or faster increases in temperature at depth (Fig. 2). However, our aquaria experiments
310 and other studies have revealed multiple shallow specialist coral species with exceptional thermal
311 tolerance under experimental conditions (Fine, Gildor et al. 2013, Bellworthy and Fine 2017,
312 Krueger, Horwitz et al. 2017).

313 Our physiological assessments of depth-generalist and deep-specialist corals suggest that
314 deep-specialist corals suffer from bleaching events due to rising temperatures that induced damage in
315 their photosynthetic capacity. PAM fluorometry revealed damaged photosynthetic performances with
316 lower electron transport rates (rETR_s) and higher non-photochemical quenchings (NPQs) of the
317 bleached deep-specialist corals in 2018. Our heat-stress experiment in 2016 further indicated low
318 resilience of the deep-specialist *L. glabra* to rising temperatures.

319 It is estimated that the top 100 m of the oceans have warmed by +0.33°C since 1969 (Levitus,
320 Antonov et al. 2017). Most of the global warming occurred in the past 40 years, with the most recent

321 decade being the warmest. The warming of the mesophotic water (49–62 m) in Eilat, at +0.48°C per
322 decade, was much higher than the global ocean average, indicating this region of Israel is a hot spot
323 of global warming (Hochman, Marra et al. 2021). The Israel Meteorological Service (IMS) predicts
324 an average increase in the mean annual temperature anomaly by ca. 4°C by the end of the century
325 (2100), under the ‘business-as-usual’ scenario RCP8.5 (Pörtner, Roberts et al. 2019, Yosef, Baharad
326 et al. 2020). A trend of continuous rising SST in Eilat has been evident since 1988 (Shaked and Genin
327 2020). Of the continuous meteorological measurements conducted by the NMP over the past 15 years,
328 the peak 2020 SST is noteworthy. The annual average temperature measured in 2020 was among the
329 highest in the past thirty years. A short and very steep peak of SST was recorded in June, and then,
330 during most of the summer, SST was higher than the yearly average and the 90th percentile for the
331 season (Shaked and Genin 2020). Minimal SST values were similar to those measured in recent years,
332 but the maximal 2020 SST value measured (30.9°C) is the highest measured by the NMP and nearly
333 a full degree higher than the 2019 maximum value (Shaked and Genin 2020).

334 In this long-term study, we found recurrent mass coral bleaching events in the mesophotic
335 ecosystem of the northern Red Sea, previously assumed to be a geographic and depth refuge from
336 thermal stress. These events transformed the benthic community, causing large decreases in coral
337 cover over the last decade and disproportionately impacting specialized, thermally sensitive, taxa that
338 inhabit deeper coral ecosystems. We identified faster increases in temperature at mesophotic
339 compared to shallow depths and with the predictions of temperature increases in the region, we expect
340 faster heat accumulation in deeper water. We therefore propose that a vertical thermal barrier
341 segregates shallow (high thermal-tolerance) and mesophotic/deep (low thermal-tolerance) coral
342 populations. The deep-specialized corals are more susceptible to bleaching, perhaps as these
343 populations were not subjected to millennia of selection and thermal adaptation in the southern Red
344 Sea, as they are still horizontally exposed to cooler Indian Ocean deep waters. Our results present an

345 urgent need for the protection of these unique mesophotic ecosystems, which cannot be automatically
346 considered as a refuge for shallow reefs in Eilat or globally.

347

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530 Authors declare that they have no competing interests.

531 **Data and materials availability:**

532 All data are available in the main text or the supplementary materials. Datasets and codes
533 available at https://github.com/gal4596/MCEs_Bleaching

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540 **Tables and figure's captions**

541 **Table 1. In situ temperature data from the northern Red Sea.** Data collected adjacent to the
542 Interuniversity Institute of Eilat by HOBO temperature loggers during seven years and is presented
543 annually. # starting date of 21st July 2011; \$ to end date of 1st September 2017; and * high thermal
544 stress.

545

546 **Table 2. Averaged Maximum Monthly Mean (MMM) of temperature from the northern Red**
547 **Sea.** Open ocean data collected in station A (Fig S1) adjacent to Eilat by Seabird CTD every month
548 from 2003-2019 by the Israeli National Monitoring Program of the Gulf of Eilat.

549

550 **Fig. 1. Vertical isolation between shallow-specialist and deep-specialist corals in the Red Sea.**

551 (A) Map of the Red Sea indicating the cooler high-latitude Gulf of Eilat/Aqaba; the eight-thousand-
552 year-old horizontal thermal barrier in the southern Red Sea; and the connection to the Indian Ocean
553 through the Gulf of Aden's narrow and shallow sill of Bab al-Mandab's straits. Average monthly
554 mean (AMM) temperature ranges were collected from NOAA Coral Reef Watch database (NOAA
555 Coral Reef Watch 2021). Map template (World Imagery base map) used in QGIS (QGIS.org 2021).

556 (B) Schematic illustration of the three observed depth-based communities along a depth gradient with
557 hypothesised thermal-tolerance capabilities. Depths shallower than 50 m act as a vertical high-
558 temperature barrier which restricts deep-specialist taxa to the deeper zone. Zonation by light
559 boundaries calculated after Laverick et al. (Laverick, Tamir et al. 2020).

560

561 **Fig. 2. Open ocean and in situ temperature monitoring adjacent to the bleached ecosystem. (A)**

562 Open ocean monthly temperature data from 2003-2019 collected by the Israeli National Monitoring
563 Program of the Gulf of Eilat (NPM; (Shaked and Genin 2020)). Trendlines show a consistent rise in
564 temperature at all depth bins, with a steeper increase at depths below 38 m. (B) High-frequency (10-
565 min interval) in situ temperature data over seven years at the study site. BL and grey transparent bars
566 represent bleaching events in mesophotic depths; dashed red lines represent the averaged maximum

567 monthly mean (MMM) and full red lines represent the bleaching threshold as $MMM+1^{\circ}\text{C}$ for each
568 depth bin.

569

570 **Fig. 3. Community dynamics across three mass bleaching events in the mesophotic ecosystem**

571 **(55-65 m depth) of Eilat. (A)** Non-metric multidimensional scaling (nMDS) ordination of the

572 taxonomic composition of the benthic assemblages during the bleaching years. Vectors show the

573 proportional influence of each benthic group on the ordination distribution. Circle sizes represent the

574 hard coral cover (%) for each quadrat (n=30-32 quadrats of 0.35m^2 per year). **(B)** Relative percentage

575 contribution of each hard coral morphological group to the total coral cover in each year.